

High Arctic Ocean Observation System

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Deliverable 5.2

Public Website including Materials for Dissemination and Communication

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The authors confirm contribution to the deliverable as follows: study conception and design: R.M. Higgins, S. Granchinho; draft preparation: R. Higgins, S. Granchinho. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the deliverable.

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No	Beneficiary	PM	No	Beneficiary	PM
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2	IOPAN	x	9	EurOcean	0.67
3	NPI	x	10	IMR	x
4	UiB	x	11	AWI	x
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6	Stinger	x	13	UBAH (AP)	x
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Used person-months includes providing input to the structure and/or content of the website. x) indicates that the time used is less than 1 working day.

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	X

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Horizon Europe programme requires all projects to carry out Dissemination and Exploitation of their results as well as Communication of their project.

Communication in HiAOOS is a cross-cutting activity that is strategically planned with a view to the impacts we want to bring about. By developing a coherent communication plan (WP5) addressing focused activities, HiAOOS will raise awareness and engagement in issues of Arctic observation, particularly with regard to cutting edge innovations and new technologies.

The HiAOOS website, (<https://hiaaos.eu/>), is one of the main channels for communication of all project relevant information, such as publicly downloadable products, news and events related to the project. The website also provides basic information regarding the project beneficiaries and links to their websites. The website follows the EC guidelines to support the activities of the project, promote communication among all partners and be a vehicle of promotion of the project to the "external world".

The website went live on 30 June 2023 (M6) of the HiAOOS project, but it will continue to be updated throughout the project. These revisions will be particularly important in supporting communication and dissemination, and for ensuring maximum exploitation of the project results.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The HiAOOS Project in brief

The overall objective of HiAOOS is to advance the uptake of new ocean observing capabilities and capacity in the high Arctic to strengthen European and national infrastructures in their effort to support new and ambitious research within climate, environment and geohazards.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Establish collaboration with existing and emerging research infrastructures (RIs) in the Arctic;
- Improve the observing capabilities in ice-covered Arctic Ocean through new infrastructure;
- Unlock new observing capacity to RIs and researchers through methods, tools and training;
- Advance observing systems in the Arctic building on subsea technology;
- Reduce environmental impact of Arctic observing systems;
- Comply with the FAIR principles and contribute to Open Science.

1.2 Context and objectives of this document

This document describes the HiAOOS website and other materials supporting communication and dissemination. The website supports all the activities in the project, especially those that relate to WP5 – Communication and Dissemination. The main messages of the project and the other complimentary communication and dissemination channels are fully described in Deliverable 5.1 - Dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) plan.

The main objectives of WP5 are:

- Plan and implement dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) activities to achieve maximum impact of the project.
- Follow up management of data, methods and tools generated in the project.

This website, together with social media, will provide a reference point for the project going forward, providing information on all the most relevant and up-to-date information from the project and in support of stakeholder engagement.

1.3 Outline

This document covers two main topics, 1) the HiAOOS public website, 2) materials for Dissemination and Communication. It begins by exploring the structure and content of the public website.

The second part of the document looks at the complementary communication products that will be produced in HiAOOS for use in promoting and drawing attention to the project.

2. HiAOOS Public Website

2.1 Purpose of the HiAOOS Public Website

One domain has been purchased for HiAOOS, which is easy to identify, hiaaos.eu. The URL leads the users to the homepage of the website. The HiAOOS website was developed during the first half of 2023 and went live on 30 June 2023. A Google Analytics account is associated with the website to track the use statistics over time.

The HiAOOS public website supports all aspects of the project's DEC Strategy as follows:

Dissemination ensures that the results and new findings of the project are easily findable and accessible, and that they reach the communities that need and can use them.

Exploitation ensures the results and products of the project are made available in such a way that they are easily used and re-used by others, ensuring that the project has a practical application to the stakeholders who need those resources.

Communication ensures the flow of information about the project to a general or mixed audience, to inform society about the objectives, activities and achievement of the project throughout its entire lifecycle, as well as with the flow of information within the project consortium.

The HiAOOS public website provides a source of content for social media, allowing a longer lifespan of project material than the fast-paced social media sites allow. This means that social media posts will preferentially link to more permanent content that will be made available for posterity on the HiAOOS website long after it has disappeared from the social media feeds.

2.2 Main target audiences

Main target audiences for the HiAOOS website (see D5.1 for more detail):

- TG1: Technology providers observing platforms, instruments, and sensors,
- TG2: Research Infrastructures,
- TG3: Scientific users of the observing technology, tools, methods, and data (who are not involved in any RIs),
- TG4: Promoters of observing systems for the Polar regions,
- TG5: Various stakeholders who need more knowledge about the Arctic and Antarctica.

The website must also appeal to the general public, assuming no previous knowledge of Arctic science and technology, as well as decision makers and policy makers.

The main messages for these audiences as well as the means of measuring impacts of communication and dissemination are thoroughly described in Deliverable 5.1 – DEC Plan.

Figure 1 - HiA00S Visual Identity

2.3 Main specifications for the HiA00S website

The objective was to create a website for HiA00S that reflects the project image and its objectives. The design specifications were:

- be in line with the project branding (logo/look) (Figure 1),
- reflect the communication strategies for attracting the main target audiences and general public,
- have a simple, clean, appealing design,
- be responsive to different devices (desktop, mobile and tablet).
- simple structure, user friendly, and easy to navigate (few menu levels).

These complemented the technical specifications, which were as follows:

- Website in one language only (EN),
- Back office in WordPress or Drupal,
- Integration with Google Analytics and Search Console,
- Integration with social media (icons),
- Responsive interface,
- Optimized for the most widely used browsers, e.g. Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Opera, Safari, Internet Explorer, Microsoft Edge, Opera, Brave, etc.
- Function in any operating system (Microsoft, Apply, Linux, etc.),
- SEO (Search Engine Optimization),
- Integration of newsletter subscription,
- Cookies notification,
- GDPR compliant.

2.4 Hosting

The HiA00S website is hosted on the cloud under a third-party agreement for a minimum of seven years, beginning in 2023.

2.5 Website Pages and Menus

2.5.1 Homepage

Special attention was given to the design of the homepage as this is the page with the most immediate impact and it sets the tone for the rest of the website. The website had to be clean and simple but also visually appealing and invite visitors to browse and explore.

The main elements of the homepage were:

The Homepage features the following scrollable areas:

- Header of the site. Highly prominent,
- Highlights carousel: a series of clickable images that take the visitor directly to specific areas of the site with updates, special achievements, new information, etc. These images change/rotate automatically and manually. This area is editable, and may have more or fewer featured images (up to 5), with the possibility in the back office to add, remove, and define their order.
- Brief description of the project: A simple statement about HiAOOS.
- News: with featured news that aims to give emphasis to four articles or events on the project. This area is a preview of the full news area accessible from the main menu.
- Partners: containing all the logos of the beneficiaries. This section links to the main Partners area accessible through the main menu.
- Newsletter subscription form: allows visitors to sign up for the HiAOOS newsletter.
- Header: very clean and simple featuring the HiAOOS logo, the main menu (see below) and a search area.
- Footer: containing the EC flag and disclaimer (essential), social media links/icons, privacy and cookies policies, and contact button.

The homepage is shown in Figure 2. An example of a page describing one of the application areas is shown in Figure 3.

2.5.2 Menu Items

As mentioned above, the website was intended to have a simple structure with few menu levels. The main menu items were:

- About:
 - i. Objectives
 - ii. Impacts
 - iii. Partners
 - iv. International Collaborations
 - v. Management structure
- Infrastructures:

- i. Field experiments
- ii. Mooring networks
- iii. New technologies
- iv. Data delivery chain
- Applications:
 - i. Ocean Science
 - ii. Ocean sound
 - iii. Geophysical hazards
 - iv. Ocean model validation
 - v. Underwater GPS
 - vi. Digital platform
- Training:
 - i. Activities
 - ii. Calendar
 - iii. Training materials (once they are ready)
- Results:
 - i. Deliverables (public deliverables only)
 - ii. Publications
 - iii. IAOS Portal
- Resources:
 - i. Communication Materials
 - ii. Multimedia
 - iii. ARCMAP
- News/Events:
 - i. News
 - ii. Events.

2.5.3 Access to HiAOOS Data Products and other Resources

Selected HiAOOS test data, methods and tools for training, other training material (e.g. slides), project related presentations and publications will be deposited in the [HiAOOS Community in Zenodo](#). The benefit to storing data and other products on the Zenodo is that this platform automatically links each deposited research object to DataCite servers. Open data and publications produced in HiAOOS will be identifiable and locatable by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) in order to make content easily and uniquely citable. Further, the Zenodo platform serves to broaden the HiAOOS potential reach as it has an established and growing specific audience of its own.

Figure 2 - First look at HiAOOS website homepage.

2.5.4 Access to HiAOOS Training Materials

A full work package of HiAOOS is dedicated to exploitation of the results and products of the project through training. Training is specifically planned to enable uptake of the technologies, methods and tools developed in the project by RIs, research groups, industry, and other actors in the Arctic through training and use cases. HiAOOS will develop material for training and use cases and make it openly available through the [HiAOOS community on Zenodo](#) and other portals used by the Arctic research community.

The material will consist of lectures, webinars, infographics, educational videos and training exercises. The scientists and engineers involved in the project, who are experts in ocean technology, methods, tools, and digital platforms, will prepare the material during the project. The material will be used in the series of workshops as described in Deliverable 5.1 (Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan). Topics to be addressed include the various observing systems, field operations, and data processing. The material will be made openly available as webinars on the project website, YouTube, etc.

The webinars will be advertised directly towards RI websites, ocean technology networks (such as GCE Ocean Technology in Norway) and the Underwater Sound Forum (UK). The material will also be used and promoted in connection with presentations of HiAOOS at European conferences (e.g. ICUA, UACE, EGU) and towards the EU Polar Cluster (described in WP5). In the last year, the material will be compiled and organized into an online course in ocean technology, methods and tools based on data from HiAOOS.

ABOUT - INFRASTRUCTURES - APPLICATIONS - TRAINING - RESULTS - RESOURCES - NEWS

Geohazards

Geohazards can occur in the Arctic with severe impact on local communities. For example, a Mw5.1 earthquake occurred in Starborden in 2008, and in 2017 a landslide in Karratfjord in Greenland was followed by a tsunami. Seismograph networks, designed for monitoring earthquake activity, measure the movement of the ground at micrometer to nanometer scale. The seismometers can also detect other geohazard events such as landslides, tsunamis, submarine slides and volcanic activities. In the Arctic Ocean, earthquakes occur mainly along the ultra-slowly spreading Gakkel Ridge. Improved observation of this activity will allow a much better understanding of the ongoing processes at the spreading ridge, and thus the potential for other hazards such as volcanic activity, submarine slides and tsunamis.

There is a large gap in the seismological monitoring network in the Arctic Ocean. A common approach to observe the ground motion on the seafloor is to install ocean bottom seismographs (OBS), which typically contain three seismometers recording in two perpendicular horizontal directions and in vertical direction as well as a hydrophone that records acoustic signals. In the high Arctic, however, it is not possible to use the traditional deployment method for OBS systems because of the sea ice and the risk of losing the instrument. A possible solution is to deploy and recover the OBS with an ROV, but that will require a costly two-vessel operation for ROV deployment to be safe in the sea ice.

There have been some successful attempts to record earthquakes on acoustic moorings. For instance, hydrophone moorings have proven effective in recording ice shelf calving events and hydrophones are routinely used to detect tsunami waves in tsunami warning systems around the globe. In that regard, hydrophone arrays in the NAMO moorings represent a promising technology for filling the monitoring gap for geohazards in the Arctic region. Continuous acoustic recording from moorings in the Arctic Ocean will provide a unique and powerful dataset to study the geohazards in this region.

Acoustic recordings of earthquake signal. A) Hydrophone recordings of a Mw5.1 earthquake along the northern part of the mid-Atlantic ridge recorded at the OBS instrument deployed west of Iceland during ICEBERG. B) Recording of a Mw4.7 earthquake in the Arctic Ocean on 08/07/2018 from one of the NAMO moorings. Hydrophones at approximately 500 m above seafloor. The earthquake was also visible at the NAMO mooring in the Barents Sea (027_2_3).

In Task 5.2, methods and tools to detect signatures of earthquakes in acoustic recordings will be developed, where arrival times of seismic phases will be picked in a reliable and consistent manner. Initially, methods will be tested on existing data from acoustic experiments during CAATIX and INIAIOS, as well as hydrophone data from OBS systems that were deployed during INIAIOS. As data from HIADOS moorings become available, that dataset will form the core of development and testing activities. Waveform cross correlation and template matching methods, which have shown promising results for earthquake detection and phase picking from ground motion waveform data, will be utilized and the potential for developing more sophisticated machine learning algorithms will be explored. The acoustic phase arrivals will then be combined with phase picks from land-based seismic networks, for locating the detected events. Due to the large seismological monitoring gap in the Arctic Ocean, the acoustic data is expected to significantly decrease the detection threshold and lead to much more accurate event locations.

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Figure 3 – Application page from the HiAOS website– Geohazards.

3. Materials for Dissemination and Communication

A set of dissemination and communication materials will be developed during the project to support different activities. These materials will be designed in terms of practicality, but also to deepen the visual identity of the project, with consistent design and branding used throughout all the products.

3.1 HiAOOS Brochure and other paper products

HiAOOS has developed a simple project brochure with simple introductory information about the project (Figure 4). The brochure is just one of a series of paper products (brochures, infographics, posters, and policy briefs) that will be produced in hard and soft copy to support communication of the project and dissemination of its results. Paper products are typically useful for distribution during in-person events and meetings. Soft versions of these products will support communication and dissemination during virtual events, and hybrid events, and will be available through the project website.

Figure 4 - HiAOOS Brochure.

3.2 HiAOOS E-Newsletter

E-Newsletters will be distributed via email on a bi-annual basis, or more regularly if content allows. These newsletters will contain a round-up of all latest news and events from the project website and will be archived on the website for future reference. E-Newsletters will be built using the Mailchimp marketing platform and will link back to content on the HiAOOS public website. The HiAOOS public website contains a sign-up form for new newsletter subscribers, which integrates with the Mailchimp account. E-Newsletter subscription will be promoted on social media ahead of newsletter releases. Past newsletters will be made available on the HiAOOS website for posterity.

3.3 HiAOOS Social Media

Social media accounts have been created for HiAOOS, namely, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube (Figure 5). Links with other relevant projects and initiatives have been established and will continue to be updated throughout the lifetime of HiAOOS. Each of these platforms offers access to a different form of content as well as a different type of user. Twitter, for example, is a fast-paced platform that provides up to the minute information on trending topics. It is broadly used by many of HiAOOS' target audiences (see below) and is also a source of information regularly used by journalists and the popular media, influencers, and leaders; therefore, Twitter will be the main channel used for HiAOOS communication and dissemination.

Priorities for social media:

- Original content from HiAOOS: News and updates from the project and its activities.
- Original content relevant to the HiAOOS audience: Relevant news and events, trending topics that relate to the interests of the HiAOOS audience, but which do not emerge from HiAOOS.
- Re-posted content: Posts from other accounts on themes and topics of relevance to the HiAOOS audience. These posts will be used to grab the attention of other organisations and initiatives (by reposting their content) and to broaden the HiAOOS community.

Hashtags and other Tags: Original and re-posted content will be tagged wherever possible with links to the consortium partners, and to the EC or to any other collaborating entity. Hashtags will also be broadly used, and a new hashtag will be created for the project, #HiAOOS. Other relevant hashtags include #HorizonEurope, #Arctic, #EarthObservation, #OceanObs, #Acoustics #Innovation.

Figure 5 - HiAOOS social networks.

4. Concluding Remarks

The HiAOOS public website and materials for dissemination and communication are essential elements to the project's Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) plan (D5.1). The public website is the anchor for all other DEC products as it is the central point from which all other materials can be accessed. All HiAOOS DEC products contain the website address, and a domain name that is easy to remember has been chosen.

The HiAOOS website and materials are supplemented with a suite of DEC channels, including social media, a Zenodo community, a data portal, and in-person activities that work together to promote the project, share information about the tools and methods used, share the project results, and most importantly, allow others to access and use the project outputs.

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